

MAHMUDXO‘JA BEHBUDIY – MILLATNING O‘Z TAQDIRINI ANGLASHIDA YORQIN YULDUZ VA MILLIY UYG‘ONISH DAVRINING RAMZI

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Annotatsiya. Mazkur maqola Mahmudxo‘ja Behbudiyning millat taqdirini anglash va uning taraqqiyot yo‘lidagi xizmatlariga bag‘ishlangan. Muallif Behbudiyning ma‘rifatparvarlik faoliyati, mustaqil fikrlash va millatni uyg‘otishga qaratilgan sa‘y-harakatlarini tahlil qiladi.

Maqolada Behbudiyning “Millatni ma‘rifat qutqaradi” degan g‘oyasi asosida olib borgan ishlariga e‘tibor qaratiladi. Shuningdek, uning jurnalistika, dramaturgiya va ta‘lim sohalaridagi mehnati, milliy o‘zlikni shakllantirishdagi o‘rni yoritib berilgan. Maqola Behbudiyning hayoti va faoliyatiga chuqur nazar tashlab, uning o‘z davrida yorqin yulduz bo‘lib porlaganini ta‘kidlaydi. Bu mavzu milliy tarixni anglash va bugungi kunda ham dolzarbligini saqlab qolayotgan ma‘naviy qadriyatlar haqida fikr yuritishga undaydi.

Kalitso‘zlar: milliy uyg‘onish davri, marifatparvar, Mahmudxo‘ja Behbudi.

МАХМУДХОДЖА БЕХБУДИЙ — ЯРКАЯ ЗВЕЗДА В ПОНИМАНИИ НАРОДОМ СВОЕЙ СУДЬБЫ И СИМВОЛ ЭПОХИ НАЦИОНАЛЬНОГО ВОЗРОЖДЕНИЯ

Аннотация. Данная статья посвящена вкладу Махмудходжа Бехбуди в понимание судьбы нации и ее развития. Автор анализирует просветительскую деятельность Бехбуди, его независимое мышление и усилия по пробуждению нации. В статье рассматривается творчество Бехбуди, основанное на идее о том, что «Просвещение спасет нацию». Также освещается его деятельность в области журналистики, драматургии и образования, а также его роль в формировании национальной идентичности. В статье подробно рассматривается жизнь и творчество Бехбуди, подчеркивается, что он был яркой звездой своего времени. Эта тема способствует пониманию национальной истории и размышлениям о духовных ценностях, которые остаются актуальными и сегодня.

Ключевые слова: национальное возрождение, просветитель, Махмудходж Бехбудий.

MAHMUDKHODJA BEHBUDIY IS A SHINING STAR IN THE NATION'S UNDERSTANDING OF ITS DESTINY AND A SYMBOL OF THE ERA OF NATIONAL REVIVAL.

Abstract. This article is dedicated to the contribution of Mahmudkhoy Behbudi to the understanding of the fate of the nation and its development. The author analyzes Behbudi's

educational activities, independent thinking, and efforts to awaken the nation. The article focuses on Behbudi's work based on the idea that "Enlightenment saves the nation." It also highlights his work in the fields of journalism, dramaturgy, and education, and his role in the formation of national identity. The article takes a deep look at Behbudi's life and work, emphasizing that he shone like a bright star in his time. This topic encourages us to understand national history and reflect on spiritual values that remain relevant today.

Key words: national revival, enlightener, Mahmudkhoj Behbudiy.

Mahmudxo'ja Behbudiy uyg'onish davri o'zbek adabiyotida birinchi o'rinni olishga loyiq zotdir.

Xoja Muin ibn Shukrullo

Mahmudxo'ja Behbudiy (1875–1919) – o'zbek milliy uyg'onish davrining yirik namoyandasi, ma'rifatparvar, jurnalist, dramaturg, yozuvchi va noshir. U xalq ma'rifati va madaniyatini rivojlantirish yo'lida ulkan hissa qo'shgan shaxs sifatida tanilgan. Behbudiy o'zining nodir asarlari, ma'rifiy islohotlari va ijtimoiy faoliyati bilan o'zbek adabiyoti va madaniyatida o'chmas iz qoldirgan. Mahmudxo'ja Behbudiy 1875-yilda Samarqandda ziyoli oilada tug'ilgan. Yoshligidan ilmga qiziqib, o'sha davrdagi madrasa ta'limini olgan. Ammo an'anaviy ta'lim tizimining kamchiliklarini tushunib, zamonaviy ta'limni joriy etish g'oyasini ilgari surgan. Shu maqsadda Behbudiy yangi usul maktablarini tashkil qilishga kirishgan va xalqni savodsizlikdan qutqarish uchun astoydil harakat qilgan.¹

Behbudiy nafaqat ma'rifatchi, balki birinchi o'zbek dramaturgi sifatida ham tanilgan.

Uning 1911-yilda yozilgan "Padarkush" asari o'zbek teatrining rivojida muhim rol o'ynagan. Ushbu drama ijtimoiy muammolarni yoritib, xalqni adolat, ma'rifat va milliy uyg'onishga chaqirgan.² Mahmudxo'ja Behbudiy o'z davrining yirik jurnalistlaridan biri edi. U 1913-yilda "Samarqand" gazetasini nashr etishni boshlagan. Bu gazeta xalqni ma'rifatlantirish, siyosiy va ijtimoiy masalalar bo'yicha xabardor qilishda muhim rol o'ynagan. Behbudiy gazetalarda yozgan maqolalari orqali xalqni mustamlakachilikka qarshi kurashga va milliy birlikka chaqirgan.³

Behbudiy xalq ma'rifatiga katta ahamiyat bergan. U yangi usul maktablarini tashkil etib, dunyoviy fanlarni o'rgatishga katta e'tibor qaratgan. Bu maktablarda matematika, geografiya, tarix, tabiiy fanlar kabi zamonaviy fanlar o'qitilgan. Behbudiyning bu sa'y-harakatlari natijasida o'zbek xalqining ma'rifat darajasi oshib, milliy uyg'onish jarayoni jadallashgan.

¹ Usmonov Q., O'zbek ma'rifatchilari, Toshkent: Fan, 2004

² Saidov M., Jadid adabiyoti va ma'rifati tarixi, Toshkent: Sharq, 2005

³ Vohidov R., O'zbek matbuotining shakllanishi, Toshkent: O'qituvchi, 1998

Bugungi kunda Behbudiy o'zbek ma'rifati va adabiyoti tarixidagi buyuk shaxs sifatida hurmat bilan yodga olinadi. O'zbekistonning ko'plab maktablari, ko'chalari va madaniy ob'ektlari uning nomi bilan atalgan. Uning merosi bugungi kunda ham yosh avlod uchun ibrat va ilhom manbai bo'lib xizmat qilmoqda. Behbudiya kutubxonasi — o'zbek ma'rifatparvar va jadid adibi Mahmudxo'ja Behbudiy nomi bilan bog'liq muhim ma'naviy va ilmiy maskanlardan biridir. Bu kutubxona xalq ma'rifatini yuksaltirish, kitobxonlik madaniyatini targ'ib qilish va yosh avlodni bilimli qilish maqsadida tashkil etilgan.⁴

Behbudiya kutubxonasi o'z nomini o'zbek xalqining buyuk jadid arbobi, ma'rifatparvar va dramaturgi Mahmudxo'ja Behbudiyning boy ilmiy-ma'naviy merosidan oladi. Behbudiy XIX asr oxiri va XX asr boshlarida o'zbek millatini zamonaviy bilimlar bilan qurollantirishni o'z oldiga maqsad qilgan va kutubxonalar tashkil qilish, darsliklar yozish orqali xalqni savodxon qilishga katta hissa qo'shgan.

Behbudiya kutubxonasining asosiy maqsadi: Yosh avlodga zamonaviy bilimlar berish, kitobxonlik madaniyatini shakllantirish, mahalliy va xalqaro ilmiy-ommabop adabiyotlarni taqdim etish, O'zbekiston madaniy merosini saqlash va targ'ib qilishga xizmat qiladi. O'zbek adabiyoti, tarix, tilshunoslik va san'atga oid asarlar,

Dunyoviy fanlar bo'yicha ilmiy-ommabop kitoblar, elektron kutubxona xizmatlari va raqamli resurslar mavjud.

Mahmudxo'ja Behbudiyning kutubxonachilik sohasidagi o'rni

Mahmudxo'ja Behbudiya kutubxona ishini rivojlantirish orqali millatni madaniy-ma'naviy yuksaltirishning muhim vositasi deb bilgan. U o'z asarlarida kitob va bilimga bo'lgan hurmatni targ'ib qilgan. Behbudiya kutubxonasi uning ma'naviy g'oyalari davomchisi sifatida faoliyat yuritmoqda.

Behbudiya kutubxonasi nafaqat kitob o'qish joyi, balki yoshlar va ziyolilar uchun ilhom manbai, ma'rifat chashmasidir. Bu kutubxona o'zining boy fondi va zamonaviy imkoniyatlari bilan xalqimizning ma'naviy-ma'rifiy hayotida alohida o'rin tutadi. Behbudiyning merosini saqlash va avlodlarga yetkazish yo'lida bu maskan katta xizmat ko'rsatmoqda.

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⁴ Islomov Z., Behbudiyning hayoti va faoliyati, Toshkent: Ma'naviyat, 1995.

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